

SI01. Outline of the presentations given at the conference

In the first thematic block of the conference, the topic of **Data Management** was discussed. This was kicked off by a presentation by *Gerrit Günther* and colleagues (Kiel), who explored 'new realism', 'constructivism', and 'the truth' of models. Their main positions were that i) the world exists; ii) it is possible to recognize certain elements of this world; and iii) recognition does not only depend on the subject. The approach they critically questioned, is modelling archaeological 'reality', as a framework that assumes an absolute measure but does not provide true or complete answers. Models are focusing on certain aspects and ignoring others, forming a consistent but incomplete mapping of the world and hence are an application of what the authors labelled "Bereichsontologien". Due to the nature of models, they cannot explain the world sufficiently but need to be embedded in a narrative which delivers the contextualization.

Building on this, *Peter Pajdla* and colleagues (Brno) emphasised data inconsistency inherent in the dualism of scientific and archaeological research approaches and how this can lead to confusion in the process of merging both of them in an equivalent scientific framework. The authors placed particular emphasis on the FAIR data principles, highlighting the relevance of data accessibility and reproducibility but also fundamental issues of 'why' the data was actually collected and under what hypothesis.

Next, *Vera Klontza-Jaklova* (Brno) together with colleagues from the MPI (Jena) opened the Pandora's Box, a grassroots decentralised data initiative devoted to the study of the human story by bringing together multiple research communities and networks from across historical and archaeological fields. Pandora offers open technologies where research communities from across various academic disciplines can self-manage and self-curate datasets that are made more accessible and easily findable by other researchers. The Pandora initiative is also developing computational methods to improve data usage and integration, plus work is being done on artificial intelligence techniques to aid in data harvesting and societal modelling. The aim is to generate useful knowledge that can be employed by policymakers and risk analysts to address present and future societal challenges.

Martin Kuna (Prague), on the other hand, highlighted the importance of large archaeological pottery collections (herein referred to as 'Big Data') that demand contextualisation, in this case with outline of prehistoric houses, to reveal coherent patterns and to allow drawing relevant conclusions about socio-cultural phenomena of past human behaviour in and around constructed spaces.

In the second thematic block, **Dating and Chronology** were covered. By discussing methods of constructing archaeological chronologies, *František Trampota* (Brno) challenged the temporal significance of pottery styles still uncritically used in Central European archaeology and suggested finding alternative ways to build chronologies reflecting various social dynamics by using large datasets of radiocarbon dates.

Gábor Mesterházy and colleagues (Budapest) focused on re-evaluation of chronological determination of excavations and surveys from the 1980s and early 1990s. He demonstrated that novel quantitative and computer assisted approaches to settlement data analyses enable to define and decrease dating biases, and therefore, push the initial interpretations of settlements networks towards a new level.

Julian Laabs and Maria Wunderlich (Kiel) opened up a discussion on reflexivity within the quantitative and qualitative methods. On the examples of agent-based modelling and ethnoarchaeology, they demonstrated the importance of bottom-up approaches to data and research questions. This can help us to reveal the individual decisions leading to specific patterns visible in archaeological evidence.

Agent-based modelling was a topic also for *Gerrit Günther* and his colleagues (Kiel) who discussed the possibilities of this approach for exploring the past socio-ecological dynamics. By comparing a model based on empirical archaeological data and modern environment with a theory-based model with an artificially created environment, he paved one of the ways for bridging the existing gap between theoretical and computational archaeology.

Kaarel Sikk (Luxembourg) and his colleague explored in his talk interactions between the settlement processes and environmental conditions. To tackle this topic, sometimes in archaeology perceived through the lens of environmental determinism, he incorporated in his agent-based model not only archaeological data, but also location choice theories from economic geography.

The final thematic block, **Social and Environmental Interaction**, was opened by *Monika Baumanova* (Pilsen), who focused on the surface survey and 3D laser scanning of standing remains of stone buildings on the precolonial Swahili coast of East Africa. The mapping methodology routinely used to create digital images of preserved architectural remains has been applied here to ask questions of spatial configuration that might have affected human use and sensory perception of the urban space.

Subsequently, *Julian Hollaender* and colleagues (Darmstadt) used the concept of affordances to emphasise the complex interaction of light, architecture, artefact, and human beings via simulations of ancient houses.

Eli Weaverdyck (Freiburg) eventually used this concept to understand the bias in the archaeological data produced by environmental data and modern land-use strategies.